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Performance of push-pull system under pigeon pea intensification

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African farming systems are increasingly being intensified to address need for food and challenge on diminishing arable land. Push-pull technology is promoted in western Kenya as a sustainable conservation strategy for management of stem borer, fall armyworm and Striga weed. Integration of push-pull systems with other sustainable intensification practices has potential to advance its acceptability and adaptability among smallholders. Push-pull is currently limited in diversity of utility mainly because the companion crops, desmodium(push crop) and brachiaria(pull crop) are not edible. Participatory research carried out among smallholder farmers in western Kenya revealed intercropping, agroforestry and crop-livestock integration as priorities for further intensification of push-pull farming systems. The aim of the study was to determine the effectiveness of push-pull system integrated with pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*) on productivity and soil fertility. Field experiments consisting of four treatments (climate smart push-pull (maize+desmodium+brachiaria), push-pull + pigeon pea, maize+ pigeon pea, and maize monocrop) were established on fifteen farms in three counties of western Kenya. A section of the plot was demarcated and used for data collection on growth, grain and stover yield. Preliminary results show that growth and yield vary across counties, seasons and treatments. Overall productivity of the intensified system was best in Siaya county followed by Kisumu and Vihiga counties respectively. Push-pull + pigeon pea and maize +pigeon pea were superior in performance based on maize growth and stover yield for season one. Maize + pigeon pea and push-pull performed better in grain yield than push-pull+ pigeon pea and maize monocrop for both seasons. Intensification of push-pull with pigeon pea may reduce maize grain yield per unit area, though this is leveraged by alternative products such as fodder, firewood and diversified diets. High stover yield demonstrates potential for fodder and residue production. Intensification resulted in better stover and grain yield in the long rain season. It was noted that intensification with pigeon pea provides additional products such as an alternative diets in dry season, firewood from twigs and stems, fodder from leaves, soil organic matter from litter and overall system resilience. Push-pull diversification can guarantee successful upscaling of push-pull in East Africa. Effect on soil fertility will be discussed.

Keywords:Pigeon pea, brachiaria, sustainable intensification intercropping, push-pull system